

1 **Molecular mechanisms underlying tissue damage and pathology in cerebral infarction: HIF3A.**

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6 Stroke is a leading cause of human death. Also known as cerebral infarction, stroke is a physiologic counterpart
7 of heart attack (myocardial infarction) in the brain. Tissue damage in the brain following an infarct is
8 accompanied or caused by oxygen deprivation, or ischemia. The range of stroke phenotypes range from a
9 transient ischemic attack (TIA), a mild phenotype which features drooping of the face and perception of
10 imbalance, moderate phenotypes with loss of speech and motor functions, and death. We hypothesize stroke
11 pathology involves both ischemic and non-ischemic insults, and that pathologic manifestations of stroke can be
12 limited (therapeutically managed) by identifying relevant pathways in which to intervene pharmacologically by
13 studying transcription in the infarcted human brain.

14 Ischemia, or oxygen deprivation involves a biochemical process known as hypoxia. Sensing of oxygen and
15 signal transduction during times of oxygen flux is governed by the HIF transcription factors. We discovered
16 transcriptional induction of the HIF transcription factor HIF3a in stroke using cerebral infarction models.
17 Understanding whether the HIF3a-regulated transcriptional program supports or detracts from neurologic
18 outcomes will guide therapeutic approaches to pharmacologic activation or inhibition of HIF3a effectors in
19 stroke.
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